

EFFECT OF MORINDA CITRIFOLIA L MOUTHWASH AS AN ADJUNCT TO SCALING AND ROOT PLANING ON PERIODONTAL STATUS AND SALIVARY TOTAL ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY LEVEL AMONG TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS- A RANDOMISED CONTROL TRIAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: There is a reciprocal association between diabetes and periodontitis. The incidence and severity of periodontal disease are higher in diabetic patients.

The total capacity of saliva to neutralize toxic free radicals is known as salivary TAOC levels. It may be linked to a number of illnesses, including diabetes and periodontitis.

The anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties of MORINDA CITRIFOLIA, a herbal remedy with many applications, improve periodontal surgery.

By evaluating the clinical parameters, salivary taoc levels, and HbA1c levels, this research aims to determine the effectiveness of MORINDA CITRIFOLIA mouthwash as an adjunct to scaling and root planing in patients with diabetes who have periodontitis.

Method: 56 individuals with periodontitis who had diabetes (HbA1c <7–8%) and were between the ages of 30 and 60 participated in a clinical trial. Two groups were formed out of them.

The patients will be divided into two groups at random, one for each of the following categories:

1. Group A (n=28): Patients with type 2 diabetes who have chronic periodontitis and use chlorhexidine mouthwash with scaling and root planing.

2. Group B (n=28): Morinda Citrifolia mouthwash used in conjunction with scaling and root planing for individuals with type 2 diabetes who had chronic periodontitis.

The Hba1c levels of group 2 patients will be tracked. Clinical parameters will be collected at baseline for both groups. Both groups will undergo extensive scaling and root planing utilizing ultrasonic scalers (SATELEC) following the collection of a saliva sample for TAOC levels from group 2. Patients in both groups will be placed on a strict oral hygiene routine, and their continued maintenance will be tracked during the trial.

Results: When compared to mouthwash containing chlorhexidine, the current study showed that using mouthwash containing Morinda Citrifolia as an adjuvant to scaling and root planning improved clinical parameters and HbA1c levels.

By the conclusion of the third month, the intragroup evaluation in group 2 (SRP + Morinda Citrifolia mouthwash) revealed that the clinical parameters were improved.

Conclusion: Present study suggests that Morinda Citrifolia mouthwash utilized as a supplement to SRP among diabetic patients with periodontitis because of its anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant Capacity and salivary taoc levels can be employed as a non-invasive method to diagnose periodontitis and diabetes

Key words: *Chronic Periodontitis, Type II Diabetes, salivary taoc level, Morinda Citrifolia mouthwash, HbA1c*

INTRODUCTION:

Periodontitis is a multifactorial chronic inflammatory disease, and its progression depends on host-microbial interactions. Periodontitis and systemic diseases association have been Established. A bidirectional association exists between periodontitis and diabetes mellitus. Periodontitis has been considered as the sixth complication of diabetes mellitus. According to recent data by the National Health Mission, the prevalence of periodontitis is about 90% in India.

Morinda citrifolia L. (noni) is a common traditional medicinal plant of the native people Of the South Pacific, who used all parts of the plant in order to treat a broad variety of Diseases, including gingivitis.

Noni leaves are mostly applied as a conventional topical remedy which enhances healing of wounds. Extract from noni leaves has capability of encouraging the healing of wounds and Noni leaf crude extract has long been used to encourage tissue regeneration and reduce bone fractures and dislocations in patients and decrease inflammation.

Noni is rich in various active components such as phenolic compounds, particularly coumarins and irridoids (lamide, citrifollin) which have anti-inflammatory activities similar to flavanoids such as quercitin and kaempferol which are antioxidants found naturally that can inhibit different enzymes related with production of radical oxygen species

Akhisa et al³⁹ identified new saccharide fatty acid ester (2-O-beta -D-glucopyranosyl)-1-O-Octaonyl Beta-D-glucopyranose) in noni plant which exhibited anti-inflammatory property.

Serafini et al⁴⁰ investigated the anti-inflammatory property of carrageenan-induced pleurisy using citrifolia Morinda aqueous extract (AEMC). The study found that, whereas mononuclear cell migration in the pleural exudates was unaffected, varying dosages of AEMC had a noticeable inhibitory effect on neutrophil, leukocyte, and TNF- α cell movement. Because AEMC activated PPAR α and γ , it inhibited COX-2 expression and prostaglandin production, which had an anti-inflammatory effect. Mohd et al. used the Ferric Thiocyanate Method (FTC) and Thiobarbituric Acid Test (TBA) to evaluate the antioxidant qualities of ethanol and ethyl acetate extracts of noni fruit. The scientists discovered that ethyl acetate extract demonstrated a potent prevention of lipid oxidation on par with butylated hydroxy toluene (BHT) and pure α -tocopherol of the same weight.

Numerous phytochemical components found in noni plants, including flavonoids, triterpenes, and ascorbic acid, improve matrix mineralization and osteogenic induction. α 2 β 1 integrin and type I collagen are promoted by ascorbic acid contact, increasing the activity of Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) expression

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients aged 30-60 years was selected from Outpatient Department of Periodontics, A.J. Institute of Dental Sciences, Mangalore. Subjects was informed about the treatment and an informed consent was obtained from every patient prior to the medical Examination

Participation in the study is contingent upon the patient's willingness. The patient must be in the age range of 30 to 60. The patient's HbA1c level must be between 7% and 8% to indicate diabetes.

Persistent periodontitis must be identified in the patient. At least one of the patient's sites needs to have a probing pocket depth (PPD) between 4 and 6 mm. Clinical attachment loss (CAL) of 4 mm or greater must be present in the patient. More than ten locations of bleeding on probing (BOP) must be visible in the patient. The patient must have radiographic proof of 5–6 mm of horizontal bone loss.

Patients who cannot cooperate or provide information during the dental examination, have had any periodontal (surgical or non-surgical) therapy within the last six months, have taken antimicrobial or anti-inflammatory medications within the last four to six weeks or during the study, have smoked, chewed tobacco, or consumed alcohol, are pregnant or lactating, using hormonal contraceptives, have used mouthwashes or vitamin supplements within the last six months, or have a HbA1C level higher than 8% are all excluded.

All the clinical measurements will be performed in six sites excluding the third molar (probing pocket depth, OHI-S, sulcus bleeding index by Mombelli et al 1987) will be performed in 4 quadrants using a Williams graduated periodontal probe, at the baseline, end of one month and then at the conclusion of 3rd month. The patients will be randomly allotted sequentially into 2 groups in each group,

1. **Group A (n=28)** : Use of Chlorhexidine mouthwash with scaling and root planing in chronic periodontitis with type 2 diabetic mellitus patients.

2. **Group B (n=28)**- Use of Morinda Citrifolia mouthwash as an adjunct to scaling and root planing in chronic periodontitis with type 2 diabetic mellitus patients.

Patients of group B will be monitored for their Hba1c levels. In both the groups, at baseline the clinical parameters will be recorded. After taking saliva sample for TAOC levels from group B, thorough scaling and root planing will be performed using ultrasonic scalers (SATELEC) in both groups.

Following patients of both groups will be put on meticulous oral hygiene regimen, and Maintenance of dental hygiene will be monitored over the course of the research. The assessment of clinical parameters will be assessed after 1 month and end of 3rd month. Biochemical analysis of TAOC level will be carried out Prior to and following treatment (ie at baseline and end of 3rd month).

Collection of saliva sample:

Unstimulated saliva will be collected after 12 hours of overnight refrainment of any food intake and oral hygiene procedure. All the samples will be collected between 9:00 AM and 11:00 AM to maintain the diurnal variations, and the patients will be asked to expectorate into a grading sampling tube. Storage Saliva samples from each subject will be then placed into sterile Eppendorf tubes ten minutes in a centrifuge at 8000 revolutions per minute. Finally, the sample which is the supernatant, free of debris, will be stored at -80 degree Celsius and biochemical analysis will be performed.

- Total antioxidant capacity is estimated by COLORIMETRIC ASSAY → Estimation of TAOC of the sample → Exactly 100µL of the sample (serum or saliva) will be pipetted out into a clean test tube, Centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min, supernatant is collected .
- Trolox standards and working reagent is prepared at (0–1000 µM)
- 10 µL sample/standard + 190 µL reagent per well is added
- Incubate at 37°C for 10–30 min
- Absorbance is measured and TAOC is calculated using Plot standard curve
 - **Equation:** $TAC = \frac{\text{Sample Abs.} - \text{Blank}}{\text{Slope}}$ $TAC = \frac{\text{Slope} \times \text{Sample Abs.} - \text{Blank}}{\text{Slope}}$ (µM Trolox Equiv)
 - **Glycosylated hemoglobin A measurement**
- HbA1c levels will be analyzed for metabolic assessment in group 2 patients.
- Normal range of HbA1c test is <7%. Patients with HbA1c values 7-8% will be taken
- for the study.

The measurement of HbA1c will be done by column method.

Formulation of 5ml Morinda citrifolia L mouthwash:

Noni fruit will be cleaned and dried at a temperature of 400°C. The dried form will be then mashed with ethanol 96%, and a rotary evaporator will be used to obtain a thick texture. 10g of noni fruit extract will be used to prepare a mouthwash containing noni in 5% concentration. This extract will be combined with 2 mg blue dye, sodium benzoate 200 mg, acidum benzoate 100 mg, Tween80 200 mg, sodium saccharin 600 mg, oleum menthae 2 mL, and aquadest up to 200 mL to obtain the 5% concentration of noni mouthwash.

Morinda Citrifolia L mouthwash will be formulated at **Srinivas College of Pharmacy, Mangalore**

Safety and efficacy of Morinda Citrifolia L mouthwash: Research has indicated that use of 5ml Morinda Citrifolia L mouthwash does not exhibit adverse consequences in humans when orally rinsed. Morinda Citrifolia L mouthwash is safe, non-toxic, effective, and economical alternative with no side effects and traditional drug used by patient suffering from diabetes mellitus. After thorough Scaling and root planing, patients of Group 1 and Group 2 will be advised to do Oral rinse of Morinda Citrifolia L mouthwash. Pocket probing depth, Clinical attachment level and gingival index scores will be taken.

TRIAL EXTRACT

5% MORINDA CITRIFOLIA EXTRACT

MOUTHWASH DILUTED WITH WATER

PACKED MOUTHWASH

PROCESS OF COLORIMETRIC ASSAY

ELISA READER

Periodontal Examination:

All records were taken by single examiner. The gingival status of the individual was assessed by recording gingival index (Loe and Sillness, 1963) and Plaque index (Sillness and Loe, 1964), OHI-S index (Jack R. Vermillion and John C. Greene 1964), Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index (M Sbi) (Mombelli et al. 1987)

Periodontal status was assessed by Pocket probing depth and clinical attachment level.

Statistical Analysis:

The obtained data was entered into Microsoft Excel sheet. Means and standard deviations were used as descriptive statistics. The participant's baseline characteristics will be gathered. Percentages will be used to represent the categorical data. The mean and standard deviation will be used to represent continuous variables. The noteworthy differences between the two groups' clinical attachment degree and index, as well as outcome measures such as pocket probing depth, will be examined using the Student's T test.

The paired t-test will be used to assess improvement in the outcome measures (before and post test). It will be deemed statistically significant if $P > 0.05$.

RESULTS**Table 1: Comparison of the mean HBA1C, Plaque Scores, CAL and PD at baseline and post intervention in Group 1**

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p value
HBA1C Baseline	28	6.77	0.93	0.022
HBA1C After 3 months	28	6.46	0.73	
Plaque score baseline	28	2.5	0.09	0.000
Plaque score 1 month	28	1.17	0.04	
Plaque score baseline	28	2.5	0.09	0.000
Plaque score 3 month	28	0.65	0.05	
Plaque score 1 month	28	1.17	0.04	0.000
Plaque score 3 month	28	0.65	0.05	
CAL Baseline	28	4.07	0.07	0.000
CAL 3 months	28	2.56	0.1	
PD Baseline	28	4.8	0.09	0.000
PD 3 months	28	2.72	0.08	

Table 1 shows comparison of the mean HBA1C, Plaque Scores, CAL and PD at baseline and post intervention in Group 1 and there is a significant difference between the scores ($p < 0.05$) compared using Paired t-test.

Table 2: Comparison of the mean Plaque Scores, CAL and PD at baseline and post intervention in Group 2

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p value
Plaque score baseline	28	2.51	0.11	0.000
Plaque score 1 month	28	1.14	0.04	
Plaque score baseline	28	2.51	0.11	0.000
Plaque score 3 month	28	0.51	0.05	
Plaque score 1 month	28	1.14	0.04	0.000
Plaque score 3 month	28	0.51	0.05	
CAL Baseline	28	4.04	0.08	0.000
CAL 3 months	28	2.45	0.07	
PD Baseline	28	4.43	0.07	0.000
PD 3 months	28	2.9	0.1	

Table 2 shows comparison of the mean Plaque Scores, CAL and PD at baseline and post intervention in Group 2 and there is a significant difference between the scores ($p < 0.05$) compared using Paired t-test.

Table 3: Comparison of the mean Plaque Scores, CAL, PD, Bleeding Index, Calculus Index and Debris Index between Group 1 and Group 2.

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p value	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower	Upper
Plaque score baseline	1	28	2.5	0.09	0.719	-0.06782	0.04711
	2	28	2.51	0.11			
Plaque score 1 month	1	28	1.17	0.04	0.069	-0.00191	0.04834
	2	28	1.14	0.04			
Plaque score 3 months	1	28	0.65	0.05	0.000	0.10923	0.16791
	2	28	0.51	0.05			
CAL Baseline	1	28	4.07	0.07	0.150	-0.01208	0.07708
	2	28	4.04	0.08			
CAL 3 months	1	28	2.56	0.1	0.000	0.05800	0.15914
	2	28	2.45	0.07			
PD Baseline	1	28	4.8	0.09	0.000	0.32578	0.41565
	2	28	4.43	0.07			
PD 3 months	1	28	2.72	0.08	0.000	-0.23584	-0.13273
	2	28	2.9	0.1			
Bleeding Index	1	28	2.3	0.38	0.252	-0.33741	0.09027
	2	28	2.43	0.4			
Calculus Index	1	28	1.51	0.3	0.877	-0.16623	0.19409
	2	28	1.49	0.36			
Debris Index	1	28	1.74	0.28	0.340	-0.25663	0.09021
	2	28	1.82	0.35			

Table 3 shows the Comparison of the mean Plaque Scores, CAL, PD, Bleeding Index, Calculus Index and Debris Index between Group 1 and Group 2 compared using unpaired t test. There was a significant difference between the 2 groups in the Plaque score at 3 months post intervention ($p < 0.05$), CAL score at 3 months post intervention ($p < 0.05$), PD score at baseline and PD score at 3 months post intervention ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparison of the mean TAOC at baseline and post-intervention in Group 1

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	p value
TAOC baseline	0.17	28	0.04	0.000
TAOC after 3 months	0.19	28	0.05	

Table 4 shows the Comparison of the mean TAOC levels in group 1 at baseline and 3 months post-intervention, compared using paired t-test, and there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Comparison of the mean TAOC at baseline and post-intervention in Group 2

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	p value
TAOC baseline	0.18	28	0.04	0.000
TAOC after 3 months	0.25	28	0.04	

Table 5 shows the Comparison of the mean TAOC levels in group 2 at baseline and 3 months post-intervention, compared using paired t-test, and there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6: Comparison of the mean TAOC between Group 1 and Group 2

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p value	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower	Upper
TAOC baseline	1	28	0.17	0.04	0.309	-0.035	0.011
	2	28	0.18	0.04			
TAOC after 3 months	1	28	0.19	0.05	0.000	-0.087	-0.035
	2	28	0.25	0.04			

Table 6 shows the Comparison of the mean TAOC levels between Group 1 and Group 2 compared using unpaired t-test. There was a significant difference between the 2 groups in the TAOC levels at 3 months' post intervention ($p < 0.05$).

Graph 1: Comparison of the mean HBA1C at baseline and post-intervention in Group 1

Graph 2: Comparison of the mean Plaque Scores at baseline and post-intervention in Group 1

Graph 5: Comparison of the mean Plaque Scores at baseline and post-intervention in Group 2

Graph 8: Comparison of the mean Plaque Scores between Group 1 and Group 2

Graph 11: Comparison of the mean Bleeding Index scores between Group 1 and 2

Graph 12: Comparison of the mean Calculus Index scores between Group 1 and 2

Graph 13: Comparison of the mean Debris Index scores between Group 1 and 2

Graph 15: Comparison of the mean TAOC at baseline and post-intervention in Group 2

DISCUSSION

Periodontitis is a multifactorial chronic inflammatory disease, and its progression depends on host-microbial interactions. Literature, suggests that periodontitis is connected to some systemic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, atherosclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and obesity. Periodontal disease is an inflammatory disease produced as a result of microbial aggression.

The beginning of periodontal disease is defined by the existence of periodontal pathogens and susceptibility of host organism. Diabetes and periodontal disease share a bidirectional relationship and is considered as the sixth complication of diabetes mellitus.¹ Non surgical periodontal therapy mechanically does in the oral cavity such as brushing teeth and gargling uses an antiseptic mouthwash to decrease the number of colonies of pathogenic bacteria, to reduce the occurrence of plaque and dental caries. One of the antiseptic mouthwash that usually used was chlorhexidine mouthwash. Chlorhexidine was effectively preventing and controlling gingivitis might be applied as a plaque control agent that showed the best results as an antiseptic effect.⁸ Despite it was effectively as strong antiseptic action, Chlorhexidine's adverse effects include tooth pigmentation, changes in tasting sensation and the development of supragingival calculus in long-term use. Other mouthwashes such as povidone iodine in long-term used would give side effects such as iodine sensitivity problems, local erythema, pain, mucosal erosion and major risks associated with thyroid function. Numerous adverse outcomes resulting from using of chemicals in the mouthwash was so many and significant, so it should take another alternative as a raw material to make a mouthwash with minimal side effects, economical and efficacious.

The available alternative was the ingredients from the herb. One of these herbal ingredients was *Morinda citrifolia* L., called noni fruit. Prior studies have demonstrated that the noni fruit was actively inhibited by *Streptococcus mutans* in vitro. The results of various allergic responses have been discovered that the extract of ethanol, eating noni fruit may prevent active skin anaphylactic reaction and mastocyte cell in Mice degranulation that induced by albumin. Additionally, the noni fruit extract's chloroform fraction might increase the phagocytic ability and the number of leukocyte cells. Noni fruit contains scopoletin, ascubin, alizarin, some anthraquinonesubstances and saponin that act as antibacterial. It has been demonstrated that scopoletin prevents an aggressive cutaneous anaphylactic response (allergic), increase macrophage activity as well as the quantity of leucocyte cells, decrease production of IgE, IL-4, IL-10 and IL-12 in mice that. undergoing hypersensitivity responses of type I. It is among the traditional folk medicinal plants. In polynesia In Southeast Asia, commonly referred to as noni.

The major components of the whole noni plant have been found to have flavonoids since it has hypoglycemic effect (reduces the blood sugar level).The Additional elements have been discovered, including ascorbic acid, potassium, octoanoic acid, and scopoletin., Terpenoids, alkaloids and anthraquinones, Beta sitosterol, Epigallocatechin gallate carotene(antioxidant capacity), retinoic acid{Vitamin A}, amino acids, such as calcium and phosphorus, and linoleic acid. A wide range of uses for noni have been documented, including immune boosting, analgesic, hypotensive, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, anticancer, and antihelmin properties. Furthermore, noni has been applied in dental field and in Periodontics, rinsing and swallowing of noni juice improves periodontitis because of the anti- inflammatory properties of noni juice.²

Noni leaves are primarily used as a traditional topical therapy to promote wound healing. Noni leaf extract encourages wound healing, and its crude extract has long been used to help patients with bone fractures or dislocations by reducing inflammation and promoting tissue repair. Repair of bone and periodontal tissue is widely known. Growth factors are necessary for progenitor/precursor cells to differentiate and generate matrix mineralization in order for regeneration to occur.²

The present study, carried out to assess the impact of *Morinda citrifolia* L mouthwash as in addition to scaling and root planing on periodontal status and salivary total antioxidant capacity (TAOC) level among chronic periodontitis with type 2 Diabetic patients. Noni has been used traditionally to heal fractured bone, deep cuts, bruises, sores, and wounds. Mathivanan et al. illustrated in his review work. The advantages of noni in health for cancer, infection, asthma, arthritis, high blood pressure, and pain, and its potential use as an analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive, immune-enhancing, anticancer, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antituberculous, antiprotozoal, antioxidant, antistress, and also a sedative.¹¹

A study on supplementation of noni in diabetes mellitus patients showed reduced blood glucose, mean HbA1c levels.¹⁸ For hundreds of years, people have utilized botanicals to cure diabetes by indigenous Polynesians.¹⁹ It improves the immune defence system, reduces inflammatory pain, lowers blood glucose levels a antidiabetic activity.²⁰ Horshfall et al.in their study on Sprague-Dawley rat demonstrated that the fruit juice of noni(2 ml/kg) twice a day

Noni consists of flavonoids like quercetin, kaempferol, coumarins (scopoletin) which has antioxidative and anti-inflammatory properties; among all these, iridoids need special attention as it showed antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory activity, antioxidative potential and metabolic effects.²³

The present study is the first to report the consequences of noni mouthwash on periodontal clinical outcomes and salivary TAOC among individuals with periodontitis and type 2 diabetes mellitus. We hypothesized that supplementation of noni mouthwash in addition to root planning and scaling could improve periodontal clinical parameters and increase salivary TAOC .*Morinda citrifolia* is highly valued as a nutraceutical plant.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

A number of limitations must be considered in the present study:

1. The design of this study does not allow the comparison of TAOC and HbA1c levels of group A and group B
2. The study should have had a long time gap for better outcome

CONCLUSION

From the present study, it may be said that anti-oxidant capacity of *Morinda Citrifolia* mouthwash resulted in glycaemic status (HbA1c) improvement among type 2 diabetic patients with periodontitis. *Morinda Citrifolia* in addition to SRP in contrast to chlorhexidine mouthwash was effective in ameliorating periodontal clinical parameters as well. Salivary TAOC levels be employed as a non-invasive, reliable and economical diagnostic instrument for diagnosis of periodontitis and diabetes.

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